

A REVIEW ON MULTI ROBOT COOPERATION USING BIO INSPIRED NEURAL NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT

Though widely discussed, multi robot cooperation is a critical and a challenging issue in today's world. To provide proper cooperation among robots, we not only need to have the communication, but also various different factors such as path planning, searching, collision detection and avoidance, miss-communication and failure of the robots i.e. the multi robot systems must work well under robust environments. The bio inspired neural network is used for cooperation in a multi robot system. In this paper, we provide a detailed literature review on multi robot cooperation using bioinspired neural networks.

KEYWORDS

Multi-robot cooperation, bio inspired neural networks, robustness.

1. INTRODUCTION

Bio inspired networks multi robot cooperative system [1-4] has attracted wide attention of research community in the last decade. Multi robot cooperation [2] is a critical and a challenging issue in today's world. In order to provide the proper cooperation among robots, we not only need to have the communication, but also different factors such as path planning [28], searching, collision detection and avoidance [29], miss-communication and failure of the robots i.e. the multi robot systems must work well under robust environments.

Since the introduction of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in 1960s, there is a growing research interest both in the hardware and the software in relation to the multi robot cooperation. In last two decades research on robotics has witnessed several advancements in design, construction, operation, and application of robots as well as computer systems for their control, sensory feedback, and information processing. Even though a single robot can perform a given task, a team of robots can perform the same task efficiently. Robotics deal with automated machines that can take the place of humans in dangerous environments or manufacturing processes, or resemble humans in appearance, behaviour and cognition.

In the recent past, numbers of research papers have been published on bio-inspired multi-robot cooperation. These papers are primarily focused on the hunting techniques in multi robot cooperation. In [1], Karim Benbouabdullah and Zhu Qi- dan have focused on path planning in multi robot through a fuzzy logic controller. Here the controller can be further optimized. In [2], Jianjun Ni and Simon X. Yang proposed a novel approach for hunting task. They have focussed on the robustness aspect of the algorithm. The authors have not considered the issue of velocity of a robot. The velocity of the robot needs to vary as the opponent moves or approaches.

We are greatly motivated by the large body of research literature for addressing various ongoing issues in the area of multi robot cooperation using bio-inspired neural networks. Aim of this paper is to present an extended review on multi robot cooperation.

Remainder of the paper is organized as follows: In section II, we present the fundamental bio-inspired multi robot cooperation system. In section III, we present a detailed related research in the area. The multi robot system is divided further into four different categories. First category includes some of the aspects of hunting techniques used for creating robust environment. The second category includes various game theory based application research papers, the third category includes research papers based on multi vehicle motion planning and the fourth category is based on the learning algorithms of the multi robot system. In Section IV, we conclude and present the future scope of multi robot cooperative systems. The last part of this section includes a tabular overview of some of the important research papers studied.

2. BIO-INSPIRED MULTI ROBOT COOPERATION

Multi robot cooperation includes joint collaborative behaviour that is directed towards some goal in which there is a common interest or reward [30]. It is a form of interaction, usually based on communication [31]. In multi robot cooperation, a group of robots work together for some task that creates a progressive result such as increasing performance or saving time [32]. Coupled with bio-inspired algorithms, multi robot cooperation may perform some task more efficiently than a single robot.

Bioinspired algorithms are largely influenced by the natural processes such as ant colony, bee colony etc. These algorithms when applied to machine learning, leads to autonomous robots. Autonomous robots are able to respond and adapt to their environments. These could have numerous advantages working in areas such as war zones and hazardous clean-up operations.

Bio inspired neural networks involve the method of specifying a set of simple rules, a set of simple organisms which adhere to those rules, and a method of iteratively applying those rules. Due to these rules and applications, the complexity of the system increases. By using combined bottom up and decentralized approach, one can manage the complexity issue. Bottom up approach is progressing from small or subordinate units to a larger or more important unit. As there are many robots in a multi robot system, along with robots there can be various other agents like obstacles, opponents etc. It becomes easy to implement if the decentralized approach is used as all the work, power gets distributed. If decentralized approach is not used, then the system will have central authority. If the central authority of the system fails, then the whole system will be destroyed.

As shown in the Fig. 1, there are 6 robots R1 to R6, which work in coordination to catch the two evaders E1 and E2. In the diagram, we also have three obstacles which the robots need to avoid for collision avoidance while working together for catching the evaders. The alliance [2] is formed by the robots R1, R2 and R3 to catch the evader E1. Similarly an alliance is formed by R4, R5 and R6 while catching evader E2.

Fig. 1: Diagram Representing Multi Robot Cooperation

In a multi robot system, there are various robustness aspects that need to be taken into consideration. By robustness we mean, dynamicity in the environment which might be unknown and uncertain. There is range of issues in relation to the robustness in the multi robot system. The communication failure needs to be taken into consideration. In addition, there might be a case, where robot is dead. Here algorithm should not fail. Another case of changing scenario could be when there are opponents and evaders in the system having intelligence. The algorithm needs to be so developed, that it must work efficiently even if the decisions of the opponent vary, i.e. the system must deal better with uncertainties.

3. RELATED RESEARCH WORK

3.1. HUNTING TECHNIQUES

Hunting method includes locating, targeting, and catching or killing a target. In a multi robot system, the proper coordination among robots leads to successful hunting. In the last decade, lot of research work has been done on hunting related techniques. In this section, we present various papers on hunting techniques based multi robot systems.

3.1.1. CONTROL THEORETICAL FUZZY LOGIC DESIGN

In [1], Karim Benbouabdullah and Zhu Qi- dan present a fuzzy logic controller for multi robot path planning in unknown environment. Using control theoretical approach, authors have focussed on fuzzy logic controller that computes robot's linear and angular velocities with reasonable accuracy. This idea is inspired from wild animals while they follow their preys. This bio-inspired research work attempts to change the velocity of robots in order to decrease its distance and angle with the target at each decision point.

The authors have presented architecture of a Fuzzy Logic Controller (FLC) depicted in Fig. 2. It consists of a fuzzifier, control rule base, a fuzzy inference engine and defuzzifier. Along with this architecture, some membership functions are used. Firstly, the physical inputs are normalized by multiplying the corresponding scaling factors. The fuzzifier uses membership functions to fuzzify the normalized physical inputs. Then the fuzzy inference engine performs reasoning on control decisions. Finally, the defuzzifier converts fuzzy control decisions into physical control signals.

Fig. 2: FLC architecture

Panus N. [20] deals with the issue of mobile robot navigation in an indoor environment. It becomes difficult to coordinate different behaviours in order to achieve a particular goal. The author have used behaviour coordination module using weighted vector summation of the schemas. The adaptation of dynamic weights depends on the current environment condition, and is achieved through a fuzzy inference system, where fuzzy rules are used to automatically generate and update the weights during navigation. This allows the robot to successfully complete its task within an optimum travel distance and reasonable amount of time without experiencing any collision.

In [27], the authors have focused on how to identify different responses to sensory inputs. Such as avoiding obstacles in which sonar information about a close obstacle should result in a movement away from the obstacle. A given set of behaviours is then blended in a certain way to produce either a trade off behaviour or a more complex behaviour. However, a number of issues with regard to behaviour based navigation are still under investigation.

3.1.2. COOPERATIVE HUNTING APPROACH

Jianjun Ni and Simon X. Yang. [2], proposed a novel approach focused on cooperative hunting in the unknown environment using bio inspired neural network by multi robot systems. As shown in fig.3, hunting task can be solved in three stages: search, pursuit and catch.

As shown in figure-3, a hunting task is given to a robot team at the beginning to search an evader is denoted by $T = \{N_e, N_r, A_s\}$ where N_e is the number of evaders, N_r is the number of robots needed to catch one evader, and A_s is the area of the searching space. The robot team begins to search for the evaders. In pursuit stage, once a robot sees an evader, robot becomes a temporary commander and involves all the other robots in that searching space to catch that particular evader. A unique ID is created by the robot which is now the temporary commander who finds the evader. All this is done to distinguish all the evaders from their mates.

The temporary commander will send the location of evader to the other robots in the alliance continuously. If the conditions to catch the evader are satisfied, according to the algorithm used by the authors in the paper, the catch stage begins until evader is caught. The algorithms used in this paper are very efficient as they can deal with various situations automatically and catch the evaders efficiently. These algorithms can also handle the situations where multiple evaders come into existence. In addition, it can also deal with dynamic tasks in the environment with different boundary shapes.

The velocity of the robots need to vary with conditions, it needs to be increased at some situations like if all the processes are covered and there is need to simply catch the evader.

Fig.3: Flow diagram of the hunting task [2]

3.1.3. OPTIMIZATION OF PATH PLANNING

Alphan Ulusoy et al. [3] have optimized path planning by using temporal logic constraints. The authors have used linear temporal logic formula to handle the mobility issue of each robot. The linear temporal logic formula works well even when there is uncertainty in the robot's travelling time and their speed. The authors also focused on minimizing the cost function because it captures the maximum time between satisfying instances of an optimizing proposition. Earlier work was focused on single robot which was then extended for multi robot by restricting the transitions of the robot as synchronous. In this paper the authors have further improved wherein the robots can move asynchronously.

3.1.4. ROBUST MULTI ROBOT SYSTEM

Farinelli et al. [19] focused on coordination in a Multi Robot Systems (MRS). MRS is developed to operate well in dynamic environment, where there is uncertainty and unforeseen changes which can happen due to the presence of robots and other agents such as obstacles or the opponents in the environment that are external to the system. The authors have well described taxonomy for the classification of work on MRS on the basis of dimensions. They have categorized the taxonomy into four different levels such as cooperation, knowledge, coordination and organization.

However, there can be large variation in robotic systems which may range from simple sensors. The authors have discussed on several different settings of MRS, on fairly complex mobile platforms, equipped with sophisticated sensors and actuators that are able to execute complex tasks.

3.1.5. ADAPTIVE DESIGN

Gal A. Kaminka et al. [15] have investigated adaptive coordination methods for improving spatial coordination in teams. The reward function is used as a basis for the learning called Effectiveness Index (EI). It helps to reduce time and resources spent in coordinating the multi robots. EI is domain independent i.e. it does not require any knowledge of the task involved.

3.2 GAME THEORY BASED TECHNIQUES

R. R. Brooks et al. [6], proposed a two player pursuit evasion game where both the players have perfect knowledge of the opponent's position. The players can also use primitive sensing models. All the previous work done related to this topic was based on the assumption that the pursuer knows the position of the evader with certainty at all times. Electronic Counter Measures (ECMs) are used by the authors to encounter specific types of processes. The processes are when slow evaders often escape faster pursuers by confusing the pursuer. Both the pursuer and the evader rely on sensors to determine the locations of their opponents. This situation exists in the real world. The authors have extended the variation of Merz's game [21] [22] of two identical cars. This problem is valid with 3-D vision also, as in the case of airplanes and missiles.

Rosemary Emery et al. [7] also worked on game theoretic control for multi robots. It becomes difficult for a robot team to coordinate in tightly coupled tasks. Partially observable stochastic games (POSGs) provide a solution model for decentralized robot teams. The authors have focused on reducing the computation time during lookahead by using clustering similar observations histories together.

3.2.1 LOCALIZATION APPROACH

V. Okadura and A. Helena [19] have worked on the issue of multi-robot localization in a group within the same environment. The authors have presented a statistical approach for cooperative multi-robot localization. Markov localization [23] is the localization approach used in the paper. It uses two models to localize a robot, they are: A motion model and an observation model. There must be trade-off between communication and localization accuracy because there is limitation in the work if amount of data needed to communicate is increased due to updation of robot's poses.

3.3 MULTI – VEHICLE MOTION PLANNING BASED TECHNIQUES

Pramod Abhichandani et al. [4] have used Mixed Integer Nonlinear Programming (MINLP) for multi vehicle motion planning. MINLP are increasingly used to address various issues of robotics. The stochastic physical layer communication model [24] is incorporated into the formulation of inter- vehicle communication connectivity requirements.

The three basic elements of the model used are: robot architecture and motion, robot paths and inter- robot communication. The robots move in a global Cartesian co-ordinate plane. The path of robot is fixed which is represented by a two-dimensional piecewise cubic spline curve.

S. Sariel et al. [5] proposed MCM operations which include finding and seizing mine stockpiles before they are deployed, sweeping desired operational areas, identifying mined areas to be avoided and locating and neutralizing individual mines. To recognize mines on the seafloor is not a difficult task but the difficulty arises with the abundance of no mine objects on the seafloor that possesses mine like characteristics like coral, geologic outcroppings etc.

DEMiR-CF is designed for complex missions which includes tasks that require diverse capabilities such as heterogeneous and simultaneous execution. This is designed to deal with real – time situations.

Mazda Ahmadi and Peter Stone [12] focused on the multi robot system used for continuous area sweeping tasks. A continuous area sweeping task is one in which a group of robots must repeatedly visit all points in a fixed area with non uniform frequency. The complete area being tackled is divided into two sub problems:

1. Enabling a single robot to autonomously perform a continuous area sweeping task in a sub- region.
2. Partitioning the overall area among the multiple robots.

In [12], authors proposed searching techniques from the submarine level, games and information analysis in a pursuit evasion game where the robots search for the foraging purpose [6].

In this paper the authors have discussed the algorithm used in a single and multi robot system both. A. Arsie et al. [14] considered a class of dynamic vehicle routing problem. J. T. Feddema et al. [8] describes how decentralized control theory can be used to analyze the control of multiple cooperative robotic vehicles.

3.4 LEARNING ALGORITHMS

R. Reeve and J. Hallam [11] analyzed neural models for walking control. Authors investigate whether more sophisticated models are better suited to a complex sensorimotor control task than simpler ones, or whether the more general nature of groups of the simpler neurons allow them to collectively solve complex tasks better despite their individual simplicity. One feature of the neural model was found out that with the first order model it is not easy to generate oscillations between fewer than three neurons, although it is theoretically possible. With the second order it is much easier and with the third order model it is hard to avoid. B. J. Oommen [17] extended the work done on pursuit algorithm into the discredited pursuit algorithm [25], based on a reward – penalty learning [26] philosophy for learning algorithms.

H. D. Patino et al. [10] proposed a fixed neural network that is computationally more efficient than the learning capabilities of neural networks that have feedback architecture. A robust adaptive controller is proposed, which leads to global asymptotic stability and zero convergence of control errors.

4. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

Applications where multi robots systems come into existence are electro adhesive surface climbing robots, telerobotic surgical systems, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), Autonomous ground vehicles, unmanned robotics for the military, inspection robots for pipelines and port security, self-organizing, networked robots, Biomimetics and artificial muscle technology, Navigation and mapping software and many more. In this paper, we reviewed some of the recent research works on multi robot cooperation using bio-inspired approaches. We classified bio-inspired multi robot cooperation using hunting techniques, game-theory based techniques, multi-vehicle motion planning based techniques and learning algorithms. In future, there is a lot of scope in this area. With advancements in the communication protocols and cooperative intelligence among multiple robots, it is expected that multi robot system will be better equipped with enhanced capabilities which will lead to an efficient human-machine merger. In conclusion, our literature review indicates that problem of multi robot cooperation is still a challenge in the multi robot systems and require further attention to explore efficient bio-inspired algorithms.

Table. 1
Overview

Year/ Authors	Based on	Limitations/ ongoing work
2013, Pramod Abhichandani, Hande Y. Benson and Moshe Kam	Multi vehicle motion planning	Several statistical models that capture the characteristics of indoor and outdoor noisy communication must be included.
2008, S. Sarel, T. Balch and N. Erdogan	Finding and seizing mine stockpiles before they are deployed.	On considering the coverage and detection strategies of the MCM mission together, the performance of the system can be improved. The system must also respond even if there is a robot failure.
2008, R. R. Brooks, J.-E. Pang, and C. Griffin	Pursuit- Evasion Games	The authors have assumed that the noise is uncorrelated, which is not always true.
2005, Rosemary Emery-Montemerlo, Geoff Gordon and Jeff Schneider	Game theoretic control	Bandwidth limitations are exceeded.
2006, Mazda Ahmadi and Peter Stone	Continuous area sweeping tasks	There is a need to find optimality bound for the area partitioning method.
2013, Karim Benbouabdullah and Zhu Qi- dan	Velocity of the robot	The fuzzy logic control is not Optimized.
2011, Jianjun Ni, Simon X. Yang	Communication failure	Velocity of the robots needs to be increased. Also, there is a need to focus on various shapes and different sizes of the collision obstacles.
2012, Alphan Ulusoy, Stephen L, Xu Chu and Calin	Optimal Path Planning	The time required to run the algorithm can be decreased further.
2004, Farinelli, L. Iocchi, and D. Nardi	Robust design.	Tightly coupled co-ordination is required in some challenging tasks, the issue of conflict resolution also needs to be resolved.
2009, Gal A. Kaminka, Dan Erusalimchik and Sarit Kraus	Adaptive coordination method for improving spatial coordination	The learning algorithms can be further improved.

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